

IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. Innovations in the field of tourism include development, creation of new types. The use of advanced experience in the field of science and technology, IT-technologies, management and marketing will allow me to improve the professionalism and growth of the implementation of projects. That's why we need to study the science of digital economy, which is needed in the world today.

Keywords: innovation, innovation system, innovation strategy, tourism services market, tourism, tourism industry.

The most important feature of any modern stage of economic development is the growing role of innovation as the basis of economic growth of the state - the state, as well as the ability of developed countries to compete with high technologies and standard material assets.

Tourism has become one of the leading areas of socio-economic and cultural life in many parts of the world. Our domestic competitive advantage is a feature of the national tourist heritage. Historical, architectural, cultural and natural objects, as well as recreational potential.

In many respects, the development of tourism resources is not in line with the existing global trends in the national economy and industry. The transition of the economy to market trends has led to the development of tourism. The formation of a rational mechanism for the development of this sector is an integral part of the national economy.

The importance of addressing the issues of tourism development is the formation of economic markets, the formation of economic entities in the tourism industry, the development of the service sector as a participant in the development of national socio-economic processes, the development of the economy, investment. International relations, including the management of the tourism industry, include individual, corporate self-regulation measures, organizational and other influence of economic, regulatory, financial, federal and regional authorities.

In modern conditions, the tourism industry is often considered to be an initiative to develop and implement. Technology, forms and methods of bidding and supply are constantly changing the quality of services and opening up new opportunities to increase diversity. The development of tourism is influenced by

economic structures, the socio-cultural status of society, the technological acquisition of new knowledge learned by people.

In addition, tourism has become one of the most important economic activities. Tourism contributes to the economic development of many other sectors of the national economy. Understanding the historical and cultural heritage of nations and peoples also includes the task of preserving them. Innovative and technological innovations are being implemented in the tourism industry component. The development of innovative tourism services is currently attracting a lot of interest in the development of the market and the implementation of important innovations.

Responsibility of business entities in the process of structural and administrative reforms to increase economic independence;

Creation of self-regulating tourism organizations;

Local, regional and federal authorities to develop comprehensive programs for economic and social development of tourist areas in order to increase the level of responsibility, targeting and implementation;

Effective use of all resources;

Creation and implementation of new types of travel and tourism services at the national level. Organizational and economic basis of rationalization creates an opportunity for the management system to develop innovative tourism. One of the current requirements of the regional authorities is to continuously analyze the efficiency of tourism activities, resource consumption and long-term growth in order to address the current and future balance issues. In this regard, the government has developed methodological solutions.

The context of globalization, the development of a set of innovative measures for the development of the tourism market, the improvement of mechanisms for self-regulation and self-regulation by the state is a component of tourism in the service sector.

The main directions of the national formation of the innovation system:

- Creating a favorable economic and legal environment (creating favorable conditions for the investment climate);
- building an innovative infrastructure;
- Improving the organizational and economic mechanism of state support.

Innovation strategy is a reflection of the state's innovation policy. This is part of the state's socio-economic development strategy. It represents long-term goals. Determines the direction, means and scope of innovative activities. In addition, the innovation strategy will cover the development of the state. In particular, the

strategies for the innovative development of the regions and national economic sectors should be integrated with the overall development strategy of the country.

The state's innovation policy should focus on creating favorable conditions for people. Development of the tourism industry, increasing the efficiency of its activities is a key task to meet the current needs of tourism companies and the population.

In conclusion, I would like to say that the impact of the state on the innovative activities of tourism organizations includes:

- granting tax benefits to innovative organizations;
- Special scientific and technical, tax, credit and financial policy;
- creation of favorable conditions for attracting local and foreign investments;
- Identify priority areas for tourism development.

Innovations in technology, technology, economics, management and other areas of tourism should be interdependent and changes for innovation. That is the consequence of an evolving world. "

For example, switching to an online booking system that allows you to get rid of the old faxing order and get instant confirmation.

The company needs to train its employees, install and modify computers with the appropriate software. At the same time, it will save time for tour operators, which will speed up the registration of the tour. The process is effective and attracts new customers.

Based on the studied methodological approaches, the management of innovative tourism is described in the local and foreign literature. In my opinion, in order to create an effective methodology for innovative development, the Ministry of Tourism and Sports and the Ministry of Innovation Development annually exchange information, and at the end of each year I think they should be included in the program. I think this will be a good impetus for practical work in this area.

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